

Granger causality between usage counts and publication numbers

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Abstract

In this paper, 3,975,602 articles from IEEE Xplore and their 313,099,560 usage data points generated during a 120-month period from January 2011 to December 2020 were used as the study sample, covering 64,633 topics in total. The temporal relationships between the usage counts and publication numbers of these topics were examined via Granger causality analysis. The empirical findings show that nearly 80% of the topics exhibit significant usage-publication interactions from a time-series perspective. On the other hand, newly-emerging topics present more likely bidirectional usage-publication interactions, but for more mature topics, publication numbers tend to affect usage counts only unidirectionally.

Introduction

With the advent of the digital era, the academic communication environment has changed dramatically, with electronic publications replacing paper publications and people's reading habits shifting to digital. As a result, people's reading behavior is recorded in real-time, and their utilization of scientific and technical literature is archived in cyberspace. Because of this, usage counts, in addition to citation counts, have piqued the interest of many scientists. One paper's usage counts are often characterized by the number of times it has been seen and downloaded online by users, which reflects the amount of attention it gets in catering to the informational demands of users (Glaenzel & Gorraiz, 2015). Usage data offers two major benefits over citation data. While citation data is scarce, usage data is copious. For instance, between 2011 and 2020, IEEE Xplore produced 2.58 million publications, which generated 10.24 million citations and amassed a massive 150 million usage records. On the other hand, due to the citation delay phenomenon, citation counts cannot be used to characterize an article's immediate scientific influence (X. Wang et al., 2013). In contrast, the usage counts of scientific and technical literature are very time-sensitive. It usually takes years for an article to get from being conceptualized to being published and then to start generating citations. Usage statistics may be generated in a matter of months, days, or even hours or minutes after an article is published online and made available for viewing and downloading by interested parties. Moreover, the growth of open science has led to an increase in the number of academic publishers and databases of scholarly resources that provide and openly display usage metrics for publications, opening up new possibilities for using usage data to conduct more in-depth and extensive studies.

Currently, the usage data study is split into two main parts. Part of the focus is on analyzing the relationship between usage and citations to create a new academic evaluation indicator that can be used to evaluate the quality of scientific research conducted by academic communities like scientists, academic journals, and research institutions (Breitzman, 2021; McGillivray & Astell, 2019; Chi & Glänzel, 2018). Numerous academic investigations on the connection between the two have been published, in different disciplines or journals, and have yielded conflicting results. In chemistry, for example, there was a modest association between the usage and citations on the Web of Science platform (Chi et al., 2019). In medicine, Examining 2652 papers from the journal *Gynecologic Oncology*, Schloegl and Gorraiz (2010) discovered that the correlation coefficient was just 0.410, which is not very significant. Another part focuses on exploiting usage data to detect research hotspots. For instance, Wang & Fang (2016) analyzed

data from the Web of Science to determine what is currently trending in computational neuroscience based on the keywords of the most frequently used publications. Also, Wang (2013) used the ratio of article keyword downloads to the number of articles using that keyword to determine what themes were trending in *Scientometrics*. In addition, Fang (2020) built a framework to locate research hubs by mining the Web of Science for 12.3 million publications and the 12 altimetric events that corresponded to them.

As seen, there is space for further investigation into the study of usage data. To begin with, the majority of the data acquired in the study is static usage data rather than dynamic real-time usage data, which prevents further in-depth examination of usage data from a dynamic perspective. For example, the Web of Science database provides static usage statistics in the form of cumulative usage counts for each item. In contrast, IEEE Xplore offers dynamic usage statistics in the form of article utilization numbers that are updated monthly. Second, most studies use correlation analysis but not causal analysis, which leads to a lack of understanding of the formation process behind the correlation coefficients and, even more, the causal role played by the usage counts in the process. Finally, when using usage data for hotspot detection, it relies solely on download counts to identify topics that receive significant attention but lacks an exploration of the internal logic between usage data and scientific hotspots.

Given the above, this work uses almost 4 million pieces of literature data gathered by IEEE Xplore over the last two decades and more than 300 million usage records as data samples. Taking a thematic perspective and using publication numbers as an indication of research hotness, the usage-publication interactions in the time series were confirmed by applying Granger causality tests, adding weight to the finding that usage counts might serve as an early indicator of what areas of study will be popular in the near future. Specifically, this study answers the following research questions.

RQ1. Is there a Granger causality between usage and publication numbers? If so, what is the direction of causal relationship between the two?

RQ2. What factors influence the directions of Granger causality results between usage counts and publication numbers, and how?

Data and method

Dataset

The information was acquired from IEEE Xplore, a professional resource in the field of computers and electronic communications (Khan & Younas, 2017; Tian et al., 2019). For each item in the repository, including those published before 2011, IEEE Xplore has provided monthly usage data (total number of HTML views and PDF downloads) since 2011. The original data of 3,975,602 publications included in the IEEE Xplore during 2001-2020, as well as the 313,099,560 usage data points created by it between 2011-2020, took us around eight months to gather (February 2021 to September 2021). The total number of articles retrieved from IEEE Xplore from 2011-2020 is 2,581,089, yielding 157,267,080 usage data points, whereas the total number of articles retrieved from IEEE Xplore from 2001-2010 is 1,394,513, yielding 155,832,480 usage data points.

Because the research viewpoint of this work focuses on topics rather than individual papers, the 155 million usage records produced by the 1.39 million publications in the first decade during the second decade were selected to be included in the analysis. When constructing a time series of monthly usage counts for a topic, it is discovered that the closer the current month is, the more previous articles are included in the usage counts. So it is important to track how long it takes for an item to get little to no attention after it has been published in order to minimize data

bias. Then, depending on the corresponding time scale, usage data from 2011 to 2020 generated by articles related to the topic published before 2011 is added. To do this, we tracked the 24,048,360 usage records generated by all 222,670 IEEE Xplore articles in 2011 for 108 months (for articles published in January 2011, the usage counts generated from January 2011 to January 2020 were calculated monthly; for articles published in February 2011, the usage counts generated from February 2011 to February 2020 were calculated monthly, and so on) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Usage and cumulative usage of articles over the months

Figure 1(a) illustrates the article's monthly use since its publication. As can be observed, an article attracts considerable attention early after its publication, and the usage counts increase rapidly, reaching a peak around 12–15 months. After 36 months, the item gradually disappears from view, and its use reduces precipitously, hitting a plateau. The abovementioned phenomenon is consistent with our previous research findings (X. Wang et al., 2016). Figure 1(b), on the other hand, shows the cumulative usage of the article since its publication, and it is clear that the article quickly reaches 50% of its cumulative usage within three years after publication (the 35th month) and 80% by the sixth year (the 74th month). On the basis of the aforementioned statistical findings and after careful examination, the time scale has been adjusted to ten years, meaning that use statistics collected in 2011-2020 from articles published in 2001-2010 are also included in our dataset.

This study uses the topic level as its entry point. Topics consist of two components: the keywords added by the article's authors and the terms added by IEEE Xplore. "Author Keywords" and "IEEE Terms" are the data fields for these two portions in the article information received from IEEE Xplore. In addition, these two topic subsets are merged into a single set and subjected to text cleaning (e.g., removing special characters and performing stemming) and topic filtering (removing topics with single-digit frequency). Eventually, 64,633 topics were retained.

Regarding the setting of the start and finish timings for each topic, we defined the two guidelines listed below: (1) to determine whether a topic appeared in 2001-2010; if so, the starting time of the topic was set to January 2011; otherwise, the publication date of the earliest article published on the topic during 2011-2020 was used as the starting time of the topic; (2) to set the ending time of all topics uniformly as the update time of the most recent usage data at the time of data acquisition, i.e., December 2020. In addition, a time series of usage counts and a time series of corresponding publication numbers were constructed for each topic, with the greatest time series length being 120 months (January 2011 to December 2020) and the smallest being five months (August 2020 to December 2020). Finally, we collected 7,447,358

time points of usage data for 64,633 topics and the 7,447,358 time points of publication numbers corresponding to those time points.

Analysis method

The Granger causality test was used as the main analysis method in this paper. It is a statistical method that originated in the field of econometrics (Granger, 1969) and is now being used in scientometrics (Luan et al., 2022; Ding et al., 2021), primarily to test whether one set of time series is the cause of another set of time series.

There are four main steps in conducting the Granger causality test.

Step1: Stability test. The Granger causality test can only be performed if the time series is smooth, meaning there is no discernible descending or ascending trend in the curve. If not, pseudo-regression will be the consequence. The stability of the monthly observation series of usage counts and publication numbers for each topic was tested using the Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test (Dickey & Fuller, 1979).

Step2: Differential. Suppose the time series fails the unit root test (the ADF test, as mentioned before). In this situation, it shows that the series is not smooth, and transformations such as differentiation are necessary to remove the unit root and get a smooth series. Notably, following differentiation, the time series must be retested for smoothness in step 1; if it passes, step 3 is executed; otherwise, the topic is discarded.

Step3: Constructing VAR models. VAR models were built for each topic where the monthly observation series of usage counts and publication numbers were smooth. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Akaike, 1970; Zhang et al., 2018) was used to determine the best time lag length. This paper specifies a maximum lag duration of 12 months. In addition, the model's dependability is improved by excluding topics with sequence durations of less than one year, topics with model residuals that are white noise, and topics with unstable model parameters.

Step4: Granger causality tests. Based on the ideal lag determined in step 3, the Granger causality test is run on each topic to assess if there is a temporal relationship between usage counts and publication numbers for each topic.

Figure 2. Share of different types of topics.

Figure 2 illustrates that 5.3%, or 3,448 topics, were rejected after the first two steps because the usage-publication time series was still unstable. After step 3, another 4,842 topics (7.5%) were eliminated. There were a total of 4,447 topics left out of the analysis because of unstable model parameters; 389 topics were left out because of residual autocorrelation; and six topics were left out because the time series length was too short. In the end, 56,343 topics (87.2%) were kept.

Result

Granger causality types: Usage & publication

Granger causality was found by running Granger causality tests on all 56,343 time series of topic usage-publication. The results are shown in Table 1. Overall, there was a substantial Granger causality between usage counts and publication numbers in 77.63% of the topics. A bidirectional Granger causation between usage counts and publication numbers existed in 31.99% of these topics. In contrast, 45.64% of the topics had unidirectional Granger causality, with "usage \leftarrow publication" accounting for 33.54% and "usage \rightarrow publication" accounting for 12.10% of the topics. Nonetheless, 22.37% of the time series indicated neither bidirectional nor unidirectional Granger causality impact.

Table 1. Granger causality test results

Granger causality types	usage \leftrightarrow publication	usage \leftarrow publication	usage \rightarrow publication	usage \times publication
Number of topics	18,026	18,896	6,820	12,601
Percentage	31.99%	33.54%	12.10%	22.37%

Note: "usage \leftrightarrow publication" indicates a bidirectional Granger causality between the usage counts and publication numbers, "usage \rightarrow publication" demonstrates that the former is the Granger cause of the latter, and vice versa, and "usage \times publication" indicates that there is no any bidirectional or unidirectional Granger causality between the both. Same below.

Factors influencing Granger causality types

Furthermore, we looked at aspects that influence the direction of Granger causalities, such as the topic's age (the start and end periods of its existence), total use received by the topic, and total publication numbers on the topic (see Figure 3). The age factor was separated into three age intervals: within 40 months, 41-80 months, and 81-120 months. Based on overall usage counts, the 56,343 topics were sorted into ten categories. The grouping criteria is that the top 10% of topics with the most usage counts are the first group, followed by topics with 10%-20% usage counts, and so on, with 90%-100% usage counts being the tenth group. Similarly, topics were classified into ten categories based on the total number of publications.

It is clear that the younger the topic, the more likely it is to exhibit Granger causation, especially bidirectional causality, between usage counts and publication numbers. For topics that have just arisen in the previous 40 months, for example, the Granger causality between usage counts and publication numbers is 90.23%, with the bidirectional causality being 71.77%. In the "81-120 months" group, the percentage fell to 77.59%, with just 31.44% of these bidirectional causal linkages.

The impact on the direction of causation for both parameters, usage counts and publication numbers, followed the same pattern. The fraction of bidirectional Granger causality and no Granger causality moved less as both changed. Nonetheless, the percentage of the two

unidirectional causal linkages shows a reciprocal tendency. Specifically, the lower the possibility that usage counts reflect Granger's causation for publishing numbers, the fewer usage counts the topic obtains or the fewer publication numbers it owns. In contrast, the possibility that publication numbers are the Granger causality for usage counts increases.

Figure 3. Distribution of the four Granger causality types under different factors: (a) age; (b) usage counts; and (c) publication numbers.

Conclusion

This work takes the topic perspective as an entry point and uses the Granger causality test to investigate the direction, time lag, and contributing elements of the temporal link between usage counts and publication numbers. It was shown that there was a strong Granger causality between usage counts and publication numbers. Furthermore, for emerging topics, Granger causality, especially bidirectional causality, is more likely to be observed between usage counts and publication numbers. In addition, the more usage the topic receives or publications it has, the greater the probability that the publication numbers will be the Granger causality for usage counts.

The research contributions of this work are the following. Theoretically, the statistical causal relationship between usage counts and publication numbers is clarified, and the direction and time required for their reciprocal impact are indicated, thereby broadening the scope of the usage data study. Practically, we use IEEE Xplore to build a large-scale, long-span, multi-topic time series data collection. Based on this, the Granger causal inference method is used to undertake empirical analysis, which broadens earlier correlation studies based on small samples and makes the study findings more generalizable and robust.

Several points can be expanded upon in the future study. Granger causality, for starters, is a statistical causal relationship that represents a correlation in a time series but not in the real sense. In the future, the actual causal link between usage counts and publication numbers can be investigated using quasi-natural experiments. Furthermore, the dataset in this article comes mainly from the field of computer and electronic communications, and it has to be seen whether comparable phenomena exist in other domains.

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